

CASE STUDY: NORRBOTTEN

This policy brief is an outcome of the NEVERMORE project. It was developed through a multi-step process that combined the characterization of the Norrbotten region, the definition of key policy storylines, expert consultations, and stakeholder surveys on implementation barriers and enablers. The effect of selected policies on key indicators was simulated using System Dynamics modelling, with an implementation period from 2030 to 2045 and two climate change scenarios (SSP2-4.5, an intermediate greenhouse gas emissions scenario, and SSP5-8.5, a very high greenhouse gas emissions scenario). Results from model simulations and the insights gathered throughout the process are the basis for the technical and policy recommendations presented in this brief.

Key Messages

Norrbotten faces accelerating climate impacts alongside rapid industrial and energy transitions, with growing pressure on land, ecosystems and reindeer husbandry. Cross-sectoral challenges and priorities require avoiding trade-offs and protecting key resources, focusing on boosting adaptive capacity and protecting cultural heritage and reindeer husbandry alongside the energy transition. Implementing green urban areas and flood defences, as well as education and training for the population can significantly reduce risks and economic losses due to climate hazards. Forest area is expected to decline by 2% to 2060, and policies aimed at increasing protected forest area and afforestation efforts can only marginally reduce this decline. Nonetheless, protecting natura ecosystems, preserving biodiversity and granting access to traditional reindeer herding areas should be prioritized avoiding conflicts of interest, ensuring a strong regulatory framework.

The county of Norrbotten is Sweden's northernmost county and is divided into 14 municipalities. The dominant ecosystems are boreal forest, mountains and tundra. Several rivers transverse the county and most of the towns are located close to them. Norrbotten has an inland climate with larger differences between summer and winter, and high variability on a day to day time scale. In the north of Sweden the mean annual temperature is increasing to a larger extent compared to the global average, and in particular in winter (+2.5 °C in the period 1991–2019 compared to 1860–1900). Precipitation is also expected to increase both in frequency and intensity. In Norrbotten live some of Sweden's Sami population, Europe's only indigenous people. Reindeer herding is an important cultural practice, but reindeer herding Sami are increasingly challenged by competition for land and environmental changes due to higher temperatures.

Main economic sectors, challenges, and priorities

Forest: About 40% of the Norrbotten county is covered by productive forest that is primarily harvested by clear-cutting. Norrbotten is also home to the largest area of old forest in Sweden, located in protected areas and on mountains. Reindeer husbandry is one of the traditional and culturally important activities in the county. Reindeer graze in forests and on the mountains, and travel between summer grazing lands and winter grazing lands through areas used for forestry. The reindeer herders have usufruct rights to access reindeer grazeland regardless of current land ownership. At the same time, owners of productive forestry land have the right, and even obligation, to conduct forestry in a way that utilises the full wood growth potential of the area. The latter usually implies clear-cutting mature forests and replanting the areas with saplings of the same age and species. This form of forestry is detrimental to reindeer herding as it removes mature forest with lichens, which are a crucial feedstock for the reindeer during winter. The area of old forest with lichens, suitable for reindeer grazing, has decreased by 78% in Norrbotten County between 1950 and 2015.

Biodiversity: Biodiversity is another key sector in Norrbotten, with a great impact on the economy and quality of life in the region. Norrbotten has the largest area of protected nature in Sweden, hosting 8 out of 30 national parks (81% of the total national park area). Clear-cutting of forest is the most common threat among red-listed species in northern Sweden, followed by climate change, overgrowth of previously open landscapes, water-level regulation of rivers and drainage of wetlands.

Energy: Norrbotten has high energy consumption because of the local climate, long transport and the local industry's involvement in energy intensive production. In particular, a large use of coal and coke in the county is linked to steel and iron pellets production. Hydropower accounts for nearly 90% of the electricity produced, but the installation of wind turbined and solar cell facilities is increasing.

Mining: The mining sector plays a crucial role in Norrbotten, with an increasing number of employees. Norrbotten hosts a significant share of Sweden's active mines, accounting for roughly half of them. Multiple new and expanded mining areas are underway, which generates additional and aggravated land use conflicts with reindeer herding as well as biodiversity challenges.

Tourism: Norrbotten is characterized by nature-based and sustainable tourism, hence experiences and activities that allow the tourists to discover nature, travel within the region in a sustainable way and contribute to the place they are visiting.

Priorities: Norrbotten's main priorities are cross-sectoral and focus on preserving biodiversity and reindeer husbandry while avoiding trade-offs with the forest industry, renewable energy production and the mining sector.

Decision-making and implementation context

Climate change adaptation in Norrbotten is primarily regulated at the national level, with country-wide policies implemented regionally by the county administrative board. NGOs and private-sector associations are involved in developing and implementing both adaptation and mitigation policies. At implementation, county administrative boards coordinate and support municipal adaptation efforts and work with regional actors. Local climate initiatives are funded predominantly by public grants from national or regional authorities, although funding is considered insufficient. While European Structural and Investment Funds support a wide range of projects, reduced EU co-financing rates hinder access for smaller actors and strain regional resources.

Technical and policy recommendations

1. Increase the capacity to adapt

The adaptive capacity of Norrbotten's population can be increased by providing education and training, while sensitivity can be minimized by improving green urban planning. A high implementation of such policies, supported by substantial incentives for education and training, can substantially reduce climate-related risks for Norrbotten's population even under the most adverse future climate scenario. Maximum benefits can be obtained by providing education and training to more than 50% of the population and implementing green urban areas on more than 25 km² in the region. Further, substantial economic losses due to flooding in urban areas can be prevented by implementing flood defences. This type of policies can be supported by a mix of local and European financing mechanisms, although substantially more funding and stronger political commitment are required.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Flood defences in urban areas	yes	yes	yes
Green urban planning (km ²)	10	25	40
Education and training (% of population)	20	50	80

Risk index for Norrbotten's population (0-1) for baseline and policy scenarios. It is calculated accounting for the probability of heatwaves, the exposed population, and their sensitivity and adaptive capacity. Dmnl=dimensionless

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Protected forest land increase (km ²)	100	500	1000
Improved forest management (% increase)	20	50	80
Incentives for afforestation and forest management	Low	Medium	High

2. Forest protection and management for climate change adaptation and mitigation

Norrbotten's territory is largely covered by forest, including both productive and protected areas. Despite the vital role of the forestry sector in the county, forest area is expected to decline by 2% in 2060 due to an increase in agricultural land, and policies aimed at increasing protected forest area and afforestation efforts can only marginally reduce this decline. On the other hand, total carbon stock in forest biomass shows an increasing trend, highlighting a positive role of forest management for climate change mitigation. From a biodiversity point of view, a clear regulatory framework with mandatory targets and requirements would promote practices such as improved forest regeneration and a better schedule, intensity and execution of operations. This would help to maintain the forest's ability to provide many functions, including preserving both biodiversity and productivity.

Ta) Total forest area and b) protected forest area in Norrbotten for baseline and policy scenarios..

a) Total carbon stock in Norrbotten for baseline and policy scenarios.

3. Increase solar deployment minimizing competition for land

Increasing renewable energy production could lead to competition for land. This can be avoided by implementing policies aimed at increasing solar capacity and at the same time increasing the protection of forest and wetlands. With such policies, an expansion in solar capacity would only slightly reduce agricultural land compared to the baseline scenario. Under all scenarios, agricultural land would still increase by 2060 at the expense of forest and wetlands. Protecting natural ecosystems, preserving biodiversity and granting access to traditional reindeer herding areas should be prioritized avoiding conflicts of interest, ensuring a strong regulatory framework.

4. A resilient and diversified tourism sector

Tourism in Norrbotten can increase its capacity to cope with climate related hazards, while also increasing its sustainability, by promoting domestic tourism and sustainable modes of travel, deseasonalizing tourist flows and investing in infrastructure. The risk index for tourism increases with the exposure to climate hazards; spreading tourist flows throughout the year and investing in adaptation and resilience not only can reduce risks by up to 85%, but also increase revenues. Policies that promote resilient touristic infrastructure with sustained investments can counteract the decline in tourist capacity, without increasing pressure for the use of resources.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Promote domestic tourism (% increase of national tourists on the total)	20	50	80
Promote all year tourism (% of seasonal spread)	20	50	80
Investment in touristic infrastructure (% increase)	20	50	80

a) Risk index for tourism (0-1) and b) tourism income in Norrbotten for baseline and policy scenarios. The risk index is calculated by combining the number of days with extreme events, the exposure of tourism assets (accommodation), and the sensitivity and adaptive capacity of the tourism sector, which together defines its vulnerability. Dmnl=dimensionless

5. A more efficient use of energy for climate change mitigation and adaptation

Climate change adaptation and mitigation go hand in hand, so that improving resource use efficiency can both increase resilience and reduce emissions. Increasing energy efficiency by 30% can substantially reduce energy consumption in Norrbotten. A lower demand for energy and phasing out oil as an energy source in transports would be beneficial in terms of self-sufficiency and resilience, which is crucial in times of high instability. Economic incentives are key drivers for the implementation of such policies, while conflict of interests should be avoided.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Energy efficiency (% increase)	10	20	30
Energy transition model	Gradual	Good	Best
Incentives for energy efficiency and lower emissions	Low	Medium	High

a) Total energy consumption (MWh) in Norrbotten for baseline and policy scenarios under a) SSP2-4.5 and b) SSP5-8.5 climate scenarios

6. A pathway to decarbonization

Although climate change adaptation is often the priority at the local level, mitigation actions are nonetheless urgent. A switch to clean energy in transports, increasing hydroelectric capacity (e.g., through modernization of pre-existing installments), as well as solar, wind and hydrogen capacity while reducing non-renewables would contribute to a low-carbon future in Norrbotten. Although marginal, a high implementation of renewable energy policies would have a positive effect on energy production, which is expected to decline due to decommissioning of existing installations if no policies are implemented. Following the trend in energy production, energy exports in Norrbotten are projected to decline consistently by 2060, which makes it crucial to integrate renewable energy and energy efficiency policies. Besides the energy sector, greenhouse gas emissions in Norrbotten could be reduced also by incentivizing the use of electric vehicles.

a) Total energy production (MWh) and b) carbon emissions from transport in Norrbotten under baseline and policy scenarios.

Policies	Low	Medium	High
Solar capacity increase (MWh _y)	50	100	200
Wind capacity increase (MWh)	50	100	200
Hydropower capacity increase (MWh)	50	100	200
Reduction in non-renewables production (MWh)	50	100	300
Incentives for renewables, electric vehicles and carbon tax	Low	Medium	High

Conclusions:

Norrbottn's core challenge is governing land-use trade-offs as climate change adaptation and mitigation priorities become more pressing. Success depends on strong institutional coordination, stable financing, and transparent decision-making that meaningfully incorporates Sami and other stakeholders, aligning renewables, forestry, tourism and biodiversity objectives.

CATALOGUE & LOCAL TOOL

Discover the NEVERMORE Catalogue of adaptation and mitigation policies and check the Local Tool to simulate the effect of more policy scenarios

OUR WEBSITE

<https://www.nevermore-horizon.eu/>

CONSORTIUM

FOLLOW US

NEVERMORE Project

@NEVERMORE_EU

@nevermore_project_he

**@nevermorehorizoneuro
peproj6779**

